

Annexure No.: 1

Written, Informed Consent Form

Title: The effect of carbetocin versus oxytocin on vital parameters of parturient undergoing elective caesarean section- A randomized double blinded study in Indian rural population.

About the study: 52 parturients who are undergoing elective caesarean section are planned to be the participants of this randomized double blinded study, in which 26 parturients would be administered carbetocin and the remaining 26 would be administered oxytocin. Pre-operatively all the participants would be assessed and those participants who are found to be unfit for the surgery would be excluded and replaced by another new participants. Side effects like nausea, vomiting, flushing, feeling of warmth, headache, etc may take place but these would be outweighed by the outcome of the study as it would definitely be a huge benefit for the community at large. There are no additional side effects expected and for the complete duration of study, an entirely dedicated medical support team with all the necessary requirements would be available on spot to take care of the participants.

The informations obtained would be used for study purpose only. Participation is voluntary and the participants could withdraw at any time from the study during the study period. Signing the consent form will mean that the participant is willing to participate in the study.

I, _____, am willing to participate in the study. I am participating in the study solemnly by my free will and I am not being forced by anyone to participate in the study. I have been explained about the study in my local language and I agree to be a part of this study. The side effects have been explained to me. I, hereby give my consent to be a participant of this study.

Date:

Signature of the participant